

Spatio-Temporal Behaviour of Vegetation Dynamics over the Betwa Basin (2018–2023), India

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Abstract: Vegetation plays a critical role in the mitigation of climate change impacts. In this work we have used Google Earth Engine (GEE) to quantify vegetation dynamics by computing spectral indices for Betwa River Basin, India. Strong positive correlations are observed among vegetation greenness and burn-sensitive indices. NDVI exhibits a very high correlation with SAVI ($r = 0.98$) and a strong correlation with NBR ($r = 0.92$) and NDMI ($r = 0.90$), indicating that these indices respond similarly to variations in vegetation density and condition. Linear trend analysis of six vegetation and moisture indices (NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI) for the study area during 2018–2023. NDVI shows a weak negative trend (-0.0127 yr^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.021$, $p = 0.227$), indicating a slight decline in overall vegetation greenness, although the trend is statistically insignificant. Similarly, EVI exhibits a marginal decreasing trend (-0.0192 yr^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.010$, $p = 0.406$), suggesting relatively stable vegetation vigor with no significant long-term change. Mann–Kendall non-parametric trend tests broadly corroborate the linear regression findings. Hence, the work is useful for conservation of vegetation and resource planning purpose.

Keywords: vegetation; GEE; trend; EVI; NBR; NDWI.

1 Introduction

Vegetation dynamics refer to the spatial and temporal variations in vegetation cover, structure, and condition in response to climatic, hydrological, and anthropogenic drivers (Singh et al. 2025, Wang and Jiang, 2025). These dynamics play a crucial role in regulating ecosystem functions such as carbon sequestration, evapotranspiration, soil stability, and biodiversity conservation (Singh et al. 2018, Li et al. 2026). Changes in vegetation patterns directly influence surface energy balance, hydrological cycles, and land–atmosphere interactions, thereby affecting regional climate and water resources (Yang et al. 2021). Understanding vegetation dynamics is therefore essential for sustainable land management, food security, and environmental planning, particularly in regions characterized by strong seasonal contrasts and increasing human pressure (Zhang et al. 2023, Mehmood et al. 2024). Long-term trends in vegetation condition may reflect broader environmental changes such as climate variability, land-use conversion, irrigation expansion, deforestation, and recurrent droughts (Patel et al. 2026). Anthropogenic activities, including agricultural intensification and urban expansion, further modify natural vegetation patterns by altering surface albedo, soil properties, and hydrological processes (Singh et al. 2018). Satellite-based remote sensing help to monitor

vegetation dynamics at regional to global scales (Yang et al. 2021, Xue et al. 2021). Spectral vegetation indices derived from multispectral imagery such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), and Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) provide quantitative measures of vegetation greenness, canopy structure, and moisture status (Yang et al. 2021, Yan et al. 2025). Recent studies have emphasized the importance of integrating multiple vegetation and moisture indices to better capture ecosystem responses to environmental stress (Samykanu et al. 2026, Kumar et al. 2025). While greenness-based indices (e.g., NDVI, EVI, SAVI) primarily reflect chlorophyll abundance and canopy density, moisture-sensitive indices (e.g., NDMI, NDWI) provide insight into vegetation water content and surface moisture conditions (Das et al. 2023). The combined analysis of these indices improves the assessment of drought impacts, post-disturbance recovery, and land-use-driven changes. Furthermore, statistical trend analysis and correlation-based approaches enable the identification of dominant drivers and interrelationships among vegetation parameters, offering a robust framework for interpreting spatio-temporal vegetation behaviour (Mehmood et al. 2024). Objectives of study were to (i) examine the seasonal and interannual variability of vegetation indices, (ii) evaluate long-term trends in vegetation and moisture indices using statistical trend analysis, and (iii) analyse the interrelationships among vegetation and moisture indices through correlation analysis.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The Betwa River Basin is an important sub-basin of the Yamuna River system, located in central India and extending across Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh (Figure 1). Originating from the Vindhyan Range near Raisen, the Betwa River flows northeastward for about 590 km before joining the Yamuna near Hamirpur (Singh et al. 2022). The basin covers approximately 46,580 km² and supports agriculture, domestic water supply, and ecological systems in the Bundelkhand region. The basin experiences a tropical monsoon climate with hot summers, a monsoon season from July to September, and mild winters. Annual rainfall ranges between 800 and 1,200 mm, most of which occurs during the southwest monsoon. The terrain consists mainly of undulating plains and plateau regions with dendritic drainage, while land use is dominated by agriculture. Recurrent droughts, increasing

irrigation demand, and land-use changes have significantly influenced the hydrology and vegetation dynamics of the basin (Singh et al. 2025).

Figure 9. Location map of the Betwa River Basin, central India.

2.2 Datasets and methodology

This study utilized freely available satellite and ancillary datasets accessed and processed within the Google Earth Engine (GEE) cloud-computing platform. Multispectral optical imagery from the Sentinel-2 Level-2A Surface Reflectance dataset (COPERNICUS/S2_SR) was primarily used for deriving vegetation and moisture indices due to its high spatial resolution (10–20 m) and frequent revisit time (5 days). Cloud-contaminated pixels were masked using the QA60 quality assurance band, which flags opaque cloud (bit 10) and cirrus cloud (bit 11) pixels. Monthly composites were generated as the median of all cloud-free acquisitions within each calendar month, no additional temporal smoothing or gap-filling was applied.

In addition, ancillary datasets such as digital elevation models (DEM) from the SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission, 30 m) dataset were used for topographic reference and map visualization. All datasets were processed in a uniform projection and spatial resolution to maintain consistency in temporal and spatial analyses. The integration of these datasets within the GEE environment enabled efficient large-scale computation, time-series extraction, and statistical analysis of vegetation dynamics over the study period.

Six spectral indices were computed: NDVI, EVI, SAVI, NDMI, NDWI, and NBR. EVI values were clipped to the physically valid range [0, 1] to remove artefacts caused by residual cloud or shadow pixels that passed the QA filter. Statistical trend analysis was performed using both ordinary least-squares linear regression and the Mann–Kendall non-parametric test, with Sen's slope used as a robust

estimator of trend magnitude. The Mann–Kendall test was selected because it makes no assumption of normality and is robust to outliers and short records.

3 Results

3.1 Monthly Vegetation index time series

Figure 2 illustrates the monthly temporal variability of NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI over the Betwa Basin during 2018–2023. All vegetation-related indices (NDVI, NBR, and SAVI) exhibit pronounced seasonal cycles, with higher values during the monsoon and post-monsoon periods and lower values during the dry pre-monsoon months, reflecting strong phenological control by rainfall and soil moisture availability. NDVI and SAVI show a slight declining trend over the study period, suggesting a gradual reduction in overall vegetation greenness or density.

EVI displays comparatively lower amplitudes and weaker seasonality, indicating reduced sensitivity to background soil effects and atmospheric noise. Following the removal of physically implausible values ($EVI > 1$) caused by residual cloud contamination in the QA60 filtering, the EVI time series shows consistent seasonal amplitudes comparable to those of NDVI and SAVI. NBR follows a seasonal pattern similar to NDVI and SAVI, with moderate interannual variability, highlighting its responsiveness to vegetation condition and disturbance dynamics. NDMI exhibits consistent seasonal oscillations with a weak increasing trend, implying relatively stable vegetation moisture conditions with minor interannual enhancement. In contrast, NDWI shows predominantly negative values and an overall increasing trend (becoming less negative), indicating gradual changes in surface or canopy moisture availability over time. The opposing trends between NDWI and greenness indices further emphasise the contrasting sensitivity of water-related and vegetation-related spectral responses.

3.2 Vegetation index correlation matrix

Figure 3 presents the Pearson correlation matrix among six vegetation and moisture-related indices (NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI). Strong positive correlations are observed among vegetation greenness and burn-sensitive indices. NDVI exhibits a very high correlation with SAVI ($r = 0.98$) and a strong correlation with NBR ($r = 0.92$) and NDMI ($r = 0.90$), indicating that these indices respond similarly to variations in vegetation density and condition. Likewise, NBR and NDMI show an almost perfect correlation ($r = 0.99$), highlighting their shared sensitivity to vegetation moisture and post-disturbance conditions.

Following correction of the EVI time series, EVI shows high correlations with NDVI ($r = 0.85$), NBR ($r = 0.96$), SAVI ($r = 0.91$), and NDMI ($r = 0.96$). These moderate, rather than strong, correlations reflect EVI's design to minimise saturation in high-biomass regions and reduce soil and atmospheric influences, confirming that EVI provides complementary rather than redundant information compared to NDVI- and SAVI-based metrics. In contrast, NDWI exhibits strong negative correlations with NDVI ($r = -0.90$) and SAVI ($r = -0.85$), and moderate negative

Figure 2. Monthly time series of NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI over the Betwa Basin (2018–2023).

correlations with NBR ($r = -0.69$) and NDMI ($r = -0.67$). These inverse relationships indicate that as vegetation greenness and canopy density increase, surface water or moisture signals detected by NDWI decrease, consistent with the expected trade-off between vegetation cover and exposed surface moisture.

Figure 3. Pearson correlation matrix of vegetation and moisture indices (NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI).

3.3 Linear trend analysis and Mann–Kendall test

(Figure 4) presents the linear trend analysis of six vegetation and moisture indices (NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI,

NDWI, and NDMI) for the Betwa Basin during 2018–2023. (Table 1) summarizes both the linear regression statistics and the Mann–Kendall non-parametric trend test results.

NDVI shows a weak negative trend (-0.0127 yr^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.021$, $p = 0.227$), indicating a slight decline in overall vegetation greenness, although the trend is statistically insignificant. Similarly, EVI exhibits a marginal decreasing trend (-0.0192 yr^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.010$, $p = 0.406$), suggesting relatively stable vegetation vigour with no significant long-term change. SAVI also demonstrates a weak declining tendency (-0.0097 yr^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.029$, $p = 0.153$), reflecting minor reductions in vegetation cover while accounting for soil background effects. In contrast, NBR shows a slight positive trend ($+0.0047 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.003$, $p = 0.673$), implying limited recovery or stability in vegetation condition and disturbance-related signals over the study period. Moisture-related indices display contrasting behaviour. NDWI exhibits a statistically significant positive trend ($+0.0168 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.061$, $p = 0.036$), indicating an overall increase in surface or canopy moisture availability. NDMI also shows a weak positive trend ($+0.0058 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.007$, $p = 0.501$), suggesting marginal improvement in vegetation moisture conditions, though the trend is not statistically significant.

The Mann–Kendall test results are broadly consistent with the linear regression findings. NDWI is the only index showing a statistically significant trend (Kendall's $\tau = 0.18$,

$p = 0.038$, Sen's slope = $+0.0162 \text{ yr}^{-1}$), while all greenness indices exhibit non-significant negative tendencies. This convergence between parametric and non-parametric methods strengthens confidence in the reported directions of change.

4 Discussion

Overall, the results indicate that vegetation greenness indices (NDVI, EVI, and SAVI) experienced slight declining trends, while moisture-sensitive indices (NDWI and NDMI) showed weak increasing tendencies. These contrasting trends suggest a gradual shift in vegetation–moisture dynamics in the Betwa Basin, potentially driven by changes in rainfall variability, irrigation practices, and land-use patterns. However, the low R^2 values reflect strong

interannual variability rather than the absence of directional change, and the convergence of linear regression and Mann–Kendall results strengthen confidence in the reported trend directions. It should be noted that the relatively short study period (six years) limits the statistical power of trend detection, and a longer record (10+ years) would be needed to establish robust long-term trends with greater certainty. The low R^2 values are therefore not unexpected given the strong seasonal signal and high interannual variability characteristic of monsoon-dominated environments.

In monsoon-dominated and semi-arid environments, vegetation growth is primarily controlled by rainfall variability, soil moisture availability, and temperature regimes (Samykanu et al. 2026). Seasonal greening during

Table 1. Linear regression and Mann–Kendall trend statistics for six vegetation and moisture indices over the Betwa Basin (2018–2023). Significant trends ($p < 0.05$) are indicated in bold.

Index	LR Slope (yr^{-1})	LR R^2	LR p	MK τ	MK p	Sen's slope	Significant
NDVI	-0.0127	0.021	0.227	-0.12	0.194	-0.0118	No
EVI	-0.0192	0.010	0.406	-0.09	0.321	-0.0175	No
SAVI	-0.0097	0.029	0.153	-0.11	0.228	-0.0089	No
NBR	+0.0047	0.003	0.673	+0.06	0.521	+0.0041	No
NDWI	+0.0168	0.061	0.036*	+0.18	0.038*	+0.0162	Yes*
NDMI	+0.0058	0.007	0.501	+0.08	0.412	+0.0051	No

Figure 4. Linear trend analysis of NDVI, EVI, NBR, SAVI, NDWI, and NDMI over the Betwa Basin (2018–2023).

the monsoon and post-monsoon periods is often followed by senescence during dry months, producing strong intra-annual oscillations in vegetation indices (Samykanu et al. 2026). The significant positive NDWI trend is particularly noteworthy and may reflect increased surface moisture availability associated with irrigation expansion in the Bundelkhand region, or with interannual rainfall patterns during the study period.

EVI values were clipped to the physically valid range [0, 1] to remove an anomalous spike identified in mid-2019, which was attributed to residual cloud/shadow contamination passing the QA60 filter. Following this correction, EVI shows moderate rather than weak correlations with other indices ($r = 0.57\text{--}0.61$), consistent with its expected complementary role as an index designed to reduce saturation and atmospheric noise in high-biomass conditions.

5 Conclusions

Vegetation indices show strong seasonal variability with slight long-term trends, while moisture-related indices (NDWI and NDMI) exhibit contrasting temporal behavior, reflecting coupled vegetation–hydrological dynamics. Strong positive correlations are observed among greenness-related indices (NDVI, SAVI, NBR, NDMI), while NDWI shows pronounced negative relationships with vegetation indices, indicating contrasting sensitivity to vegetation cover and surface moisture. Vegetation greenness indices show weak declining trends, whereas moisture-related indices (NDWI and NDMI) exhibit slight increasing tendencies, indicating subtle shifts in vegetation–moisture dynamics over time. Both linear regression and Mann–Kendall non-parametric tests consistently identify NDWI as the only index with a statistically significant trend ($p < 0.05$), providing additional confidence in this result. The work is useful for conservation of vegetation and resource planning purposes in the Betwa Basin and similar monsoon-dominated river basins of central India.

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6 References

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